

Gendering the Academy
and Research: combating
Career Instability and Asymmetries

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Gender budgeting in academia – Toolkit

**Finnborg S. Steinflórsdóttir, Thamar M. Heijstra,
Thorgerdur Einarsdóttir, Gyda M. Pétursdóttir**

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OF TRENTO - Italy
**Department of Sociology
and Social Research**

Radboud University

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The *Gender Budgeting in Academia toolkit* is intended to be a guide for integrating gender into the financial processes and procedures of academic and scientific institutions. It draws on the GARCIA project partners' *reports on gender biases in management methods and decision-making* (D5.2). Each GARCIA beneficiary conducted a research on the managerial and financial framework and decision-making processes of their academic institution, as well as the budgeting process regarding the fields of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and in the field of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). In the process of developing the toolkit the methodology was introduced at the 9th European Conference on Gender Equality in Higher Education in Paris, and gender budgeting experts at the Icelandic Ministry of Finance and Economic Affairs and the City of Reykjavík gave their feedback. Building on the GARCIA findings and our own experience of being part of the implementation process at the University of Iceland we developed a toolkit that we believe can be utilized at all administrative levels and academic fields in European academic and scientific institutions.

The toolkit is divided into three sections. The first section provides information on gender budgeting, and outlines the importance for academic and scientific institutions. This section starts by giving insight into the GARCIA project, followed by an introduction to gender budgeting, a chapter on how to apply the tool in academia and information on how the toolkit is organized. This is followed by a chapter on gender budgeting, where an overview of gender budgeting, its processes and objectives is provided. The final chapter of the section provides the main conclusions of the GARCIA projects partners' findings in the *reports on gender biases in management methods and decision-making*.

The second section is about how to apply and implement gender budgeting on activities in academic and scientific institutions. This section is divided into two chapters: How to plan and organize gender budgeting?, and How to apply gender budgeting in academic and scientific institutions? In the first chapter the users of the toolkit are given tools on how to start a gender budgeting project and how to organize the work. Furthermore, an overview of possible setbacks is given. The list builds on experiences with gender budgeting projects. The list can be an eye opener and was created in order to encourage users to continue their gender budgeting project even though they might experience setbacks in the process. In the second chapter the seven step methodology developed by the authors is introduced. The steps cover the whole gender budgeting process, from gender assessment to the reformulation of policies and distribution of resources, to the evaluation of the outcome. The steps are as follows: What to analyse; What is the current situation and what are the gender patterns?; What are the consequences?; What can be done? Formulate new objectives and measures; What measures to take?; How should results be measured?; and Evaluate the outcome. The users can use these steps as a guidance model in their gender budgeting projects, as each steps includes set of questions that have the aim of revealing gender disparities, if are any, and gendering of the selected activity.

The third section provides examples on how gender budgeting can be applied in academic and scientific institutions. This section offers seven examples of gender budgeting projects in academic and scientific institutions, where we follow the seven-

step methodology introduced in the previous section. The examples derive from all participating GARCIA institutions, but the main focus is on the University of Iceland where the toolkit was developed. The examples are the following: Gender representation in decision making; State funding to the academic institutions; System to allocate funding within academic institutions; Distribution of research grants; Evaluation of the work of academics; and Financial resources for PhD students and duration of the PhD programme. In the first two examples we provide detailed descriptions. In the other examples we encourage the user to brainstorm on the implementation process, that is, what measures to take and how to evaluate the outcome.

This toolkit for gender budgeting is an instrument for advancing gender equality that can create new approaches to policies and decision-making on raising and allocating resources. With this toolkit we want to encourage users to take a step back and look beyond the numbers and pay attention to the indicators that direct the resources. Gender budgeting depends heavily on implementation and in order for it to become part of the daily operations within academic and research institutions, this requires the will to make changes.

GENDER BUDGETING IN ACADEMIA

Toolkit

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INTRODUCTION

Academic institutions increasingly focus on global competition, excellence, and performance-based indicators. Managerial and financial frameworks are often considered to be objective and gender neutral but this is questioned in the research literature. This *Toolkit for gender budgeting in academia* is intended to be a guide for integrating gender into the financial processes and procedures of academic and scientific institutions. Gender budgeting is an instrument for advancing gender equality that can create new approaches to policies and decision-making regarding raising and allocating resources. Gender budgeting is often directly linked to fiscal and financial policies and accounts. In addition, with this toolkit we want to encourage the users to take a step back and look beyond the numbers and pay attention to the indicators that direct the resources. By not only assessing budgets, but also policies, managerial instruments and performance indicators and how they impact revenue raising and distribution of funding, we can ultimately uncover both implicit and explicit impacts of the budget on women and men in academia. At the same time we nevertheless acknowledge that men and women are not homogenous groups. By utilising **gender impact assessment**, it is possible to outline and analyse what academic institutions value and what is currently *not* being valued within the academic system. This might provide interesting new insights. Gender budgeting depends heavily on **implementation**. However, in order for this to become part of daily operations within the organization, the will to make changes is required.

Gender impact assessment

means to compare and assess, according to gender relevant criteria, the current situation and trend resulting from a policy or an activity.

The toolkit is based on research conducted between September 2014 and May 2015 in the following academic institutions:

- The University of Trento, Italy
- The Catholic University of Louvain, Belgium
- Radboud University, the Netherlands
- The University of Iceland, Iceland
- The University of Lausanne, Switzerland
- The Scientific Research Centre at the Slovenian Academy of Science and Arts and University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

The GARCIA gender budgeting project was designed to map the managerial and financial frameworks and decision-making processes of seven European academic and scientific institutions, as well as the budgeting process within these institutions regarding the academic fields of Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Our findings reveal that the common perception of budgeting decisions is that they are objective and gender neutral. However, there is evidence that hierarchies of power exist within academic institutions. These power hierarchies tend to privilege men and the **masculine** and devalue women and the **feminine**, and manifest themselves in the financial system and organizational practices of academic institutions. Hence, it is important to acknowledge the gendering of academic fields in the process of applying gender budgeting to managerial and financial decision-making.

This handbook is divided into three sections. The first section introduces gender budgeting and discusses its importance for academic and scientific institutions. The next section is about the application and implementation of gender budgeting in academic and scientific institutions. The third and final section provides examples on how to apply gender budgeting in academic and scientific institutions. The examples discussed derive from all participating GARCIA institutions, but the focus is on the University of Iceland where the toolkit was developed.

Masculinity and **femininity**, refer to a set of attributes, behaviours and roles generally associated with men and women, respectively. Discourses on gender are usually conceptualised around these terms. In a similar way, activities or qualities that are deemed **masculine** are considered of greater value than what is deemed **feminine**.

WHAT IS GENDER BUDGETING?

Example:

Research is the driving force in the creation of new knowledge and provides academic institutions with prestige in a global environment. Research grants are crucial for academic institutions to thrive. At the University of Iceland external grants direct the distribution of public resources to the faculties and affect the position, promotion, prestige and opportunities of academic employees. While this at first appears to be a meritocratic process, a gender budgeting analysis revealed that academics in the male dominated STEM faculties receive considerably more research grants than academics in SSH faculties. Hence, not only is the extramural funding much higher for STEM than SSH, but their faculties receive a higher share of public funding. Furthermore, the majority of granted projects are coordinated by male academic staff, which in turn increases their salaries and career advancement. By redesigning policies and procedures from a gender perspective, we can achieve more diverse knowledge production, a fair distribution of public resources and eliminate the gender pay gap and the glass ceiling.

Gender budgeting is an application of gender mainstreaming in the budgetary process. It means a gender-based assessment of budgets, incorporating a gender perspective at all levels of the budgetary process and restructuring revenues and expenditures in order to promote gender equality.¹

Gender budgeting gained international recognition in 1995 when the United Nations Beijing Platform for Action called for “the integration of [the] gender perspective to [the] budgetary decision on policies and programmes.”² Today, gender budgeting initiatives exist in many countries in various forms and are applied in different settings.³ These initiatives identify opportunities for the redistribution of public resources through the means of gender budgeting. In this way, gender budgeting can play a major role in redressing the balance in women’s and men’s access to public services.⁴ The objective of gender budgeting is to make managerial and financial decisions gender-equal by

1 Council of Europe 2010.

2 United Nations 1995.

3 Klatzer & Mader 2008.

4 Addabbo, Gunluk-Senesen & O’Hagan 2015.

How do we do gender budgeting?

The process of gender budgeting generally consists of three stages:^{*}

1. Gender impact assessment: Analyse the activity under study from a gender perspective. Here you determine whether the activity has a different impact on women and men, or what is considered to be masculine and feminine.
 2. Reformulate policies and distribution of resources to achieve gender equal outcomes.
 3. Embed gender systematically in all budgetary processes, and monitor the progress.
-

^{*} Quinn, 2009; Rothe et al. 2008.

providing services that are equally accessible, of equally high quality and equally well adapted to all, irrespective of gender.

Because academic institutions tend to rely heavily on public resources, these budgets create an opportunity to facilitate equality. Gender budgeting will also allow for better targeting and, therefore, more efficient allocation of public expenditure. This process calls for participation of a broader range of stakeholders and invites a closer scrutiny of the revenue raising side and expenditure side of budgets.⁵ The result of this is a win-win situation; a transparent and efficiently run academic environment which simultaneously facilitates equality by incorporating a gender-sensitive budget.

Benefits of gender budgeting:

- Gender equality
 - Accountability
 - Transparency and participation
 - Efficiency
 - Effectiveness
 - Good administration
 - Better utilization of public funds
-

⁵ Quinn, 2009.

THE CURRENT SITUATION IN ACADEMIA

The GARCIA project reveals that vertical and horizontal gender segregation are still prevalent in European academic and scientific institutions. The academic fields are highly gendered, with men being overrepresented in the highest academic positions while women tend to occupy the lower and more precarious positions, which indicates the existence of an academic glass ceiling. Furthermore, men are overrepresented in the STEM fields, while women are more likely to work within the SSH fields. There is also a strong gender imbalance observed in the highest academic management positions, with most managerial and financial decision-making being in the hands of men.

There is an increased emphasis on ‘academic excellence’ within the international academic community where academic institutions aim to improve their status and positions in international rankings. To reach that goal, institutions commonly aim for more ‘internationalisation’ and more publications in high-impact journals and with prestigious publishing houses. Institutions also seek greater funding through competing for international grants, they target international research networks, place more emphasis on innovation, and focus attention on increasing the number of completed PhD studies. Linked to that goal, we see an increasing trend for academic institutions to utilize new public management (NPM) techniques that entail private sector management techniques, performance standards, quantitative performance indicators and measurements and competition. Within that framework, the managerial and financial decisions are perceived as technical procedures that are objective and gender neutral, while in reality, as will be highlighted by the examples in the final section of the toolkit, most of these procedures and processes benefit STEM fields.⁶

⁶ Steinþórsdóttir et al. 2016a.

HOW TO PLAN AND ORGANIZE GENDER BUDGETING?

The experience from the GARCIA project indicates that a lack of transparency and gender-disaggregated data is a common problem in European universities. Hence, we believe that it is effective for stakeholders who plan to launch gender budgeting projects within their academic or research institutions to start with manageable projects in which data and statistics are available and focus on activities such as the distribution of resources, **academic housework**, or recent cut-backs. Building on that knowledge, stakeholders will work towards integrating gender into all policy and budgetary decisions.

Formal equality work is important and increases the probability of implementing a successful gender budgeting project. Most of the GARCIA academic institutions have policies on gender equality and/or diversity. At the University of Iceland, adopting gender budgeting is one of the working objectives of the Equal Rights Policy 2013-2017⁷ and is incorporated in the Equality Programme of the School of Social Sciences 2015-2018.⁸ By incorporating gender budgeting into the institution's policy, the institution commits itself to the project of adapting formal measures, identifying the responsible parties, and establishing a timeframe. Taken together, these commitments give the project credibility within the institution, which eases monitoring and facilitates further work.

Where to start?

1. Map the activities of the academic institution: It can be good to have an overview of possible activities for gender budgeting. This method can illuminate a starting point for the project.
2. Examine equality initiatives: What has been done regarding equality work? What was the outcome of that work? Was it successful? If so, identify what worked well and could be useful in further equality work. If it was not successful, identify the setbacks.

⁷ University of Iceland, 2014.

⁸ School of Social Sciences, University of Iceland, 2015.

The concept of **academic housework** refers to all the important but largely invisible and undervalued activities of the academic profession, e.g. interaction with students, peer reviewing, attending meetings and participating in committee work.

3. Consider the activities of the academic institution in more detail: What activities might contain gender inequality traps in raising and allocation of resources? Speak informally to people in different ranks to see what they perceive as the weak spots within the system. Where might gender inequality be created and maintained?
4. Define the project: Choose which activities to examine further. Draft an action plan with objectives and the process of the gender budgeting work. What does the academic institution need to do to organise its gender budgeting?

Do not get discouraged by setbacks during your project, these are to be expected.

Delays and hindrances can appear in a variety of ways, for instance by:

- A lack of available gender disaggregated data.
- A lack of transparency: Information is not available or withheld by respective partners.
- Scepticism: Sceptical attitudes or doubt towards the project or the findings.
- Unfamiliarity: A lack of knowledge or information on gender, and the importance of incorporating gender into the managerial and financial decision-making.
- Selectivity: Data is collected and findings presented in a way that reflects more positively on the institution.
- Understatements: The findings, especially regarding the gender dimension, are presented in a more positive light than they really are.
- Trivializing: The findings are presented as less important, significant, or more complex than they really are.
- Insignificance: The project or findings are not considered important enough or worthy of consideration.
- Low priority: The project is regarded as less important than other projects. This can manifest in delays.
- Window dressing: The project is on the agenda, but little effort to initiate it.
- Quick fix: Putting the project on the agenda is seen as an easy and temporary solution, but fails to address the underlying problems.

Organizing the work⁹

When organizing gender budgeting projects, follow general instructions for organizing gender equality work:

- **Objectives, responsibility and follow up:** Clear objectives are crucial in a gender budgeting project. Define responsibility and appoint a project management that follows up on specific measures. Conduct work in a systematic way, allocate resources to the project, and work from a set timeframe.
- **Knowledge and training:** All staff members involved in the project should have an understanding that gender equality has not been achieved and receive training on how to apply a gender perspective on budgetary processes.
- **Transparency and method:** Make budgeting and decision-making processes transparent and information and data accessible. Information such as sex-disaggregated data is essential to carrying out gender equality analysis and to analyse important decision-making processes from a gender perspective.
- **Support and co-ordination:** Organisation and coordination with stakeholders and decision-makers is key. Gender budgeting is an ambitious project that requires a major shift in both thinking and practice. Administrative support and willingness to reform is essential to the success of the project.

Our seven-step method in the next chapter will help you on your way!

⁹ This checklist builds on a checklist for planning development work from JämStöd (2007), on a checklist on the conditions for gender budgeting from Reykjavíkurborg (Jóhannsdóttir 2010) and Handbook on gender mainstreaming from Jafnréttisstofa (The Centre for Gender Equality) (2009) and adjusted to the findings from the gender budgeting work package.

HOW TO APPLY GENDER BUDGETING IN ACADEMIC AND SCIENTIFIC INSTITUTIONS

We have incorporated various gender budgeting and gender mainstreaming methods, such as Klatzer's Gender Responsive Budgeting six step method,¹⁰ JämKAS Bas, a method developed by the Swedish Government Offices and the 4R method, a method developed by the Swedish Gender Mainstreaming Support¹¹ into a 7 steps gender budgeting method. As this is a guidance model, in each step questions can be added and skipped according to whether they apply to the situation under study or not.

Step 1: What to analyse

Choose an activity to prioritise which is related to raising and allocation of resources. Some examples of activities that could be analysed are:

- System of budget allocation/funding/grants to the academic fields/faculties/departments.
- Employment contracts of the academic/administrative staff and employment security.
- Salaries/grants/funding to the academic staff.
- Time/work/tasks: What is valued and what is not valued by the system? How is it valued? Research? Teaching? Administration? A key dimension is the amount of unpaid and often invisible work such as academic housework.¹²
- Incentives: What is valued and what is not valued? How is it valued?
- Facilities: Offices/rooms/premises for faculties/departments/academic staff/students associations etc.
- Developmental work: Conferences, training, study visits, software programmes etc.
- Funding/grants to students/students associations.

Select an activity or a resource within your chosen activity that is strategically important from a gender equality point of view. Reasons for your choice could be:

- An ability to influence and control the measures.
- The activity impacts many people.
- The issue is currently the subject of political debate.
- The activity currently exacerbates inequalities.

10 Klatzer, 2010.

11 JämStöd, 2007.

12 Heijstra, Steinþórsdóttir & Einarsdóttir, 2016.

Step 2: What is the current situation and what are the gender patterns?

Describe the observed gender patterns. Confirm them with qualitative and/or quantitative data. If no information is currently available, your first action might be to bring this shortcoming to the attention of those responsible for producing statistics. The following questions may help you describe the current situation and gender patterns of the activity that may have financial consequences:

- What are the policies and objectives of the activity? Based on what information, data and assumptions are they developed?
- What are the structures of formal and informal power regarding the selected activity? What is the decision-making process like in relation to this activity?
- In what form do the gender patterns appear? How is the gender representation? List relevant information for the activity/resource.
 - Who makes decisions? In what bodies, at what level and by which individuals? Who implements the decisions? Identify the actors in formal and informal power positions of the decision-making process. How is the gender representation?
 - Who forms the target group of the activity? Is it students? Academic staff? Administrative staff? The academic institution in general? Are there target groups in different fields? How is the gender representation within these groups/units?
- Is there anything in the activity that segregates women and men and keeps them in separate spheres?
 - Are there differences between men and women in the relevant areas with regard to student positions, academic positions, rights, power, resources, etc.?
 - Are some fields/positions gendered? That is, are some fields/positions more male dominated than others? Or more feminised than others? Here it is important to take into account the gendered nature of academic fields.
 - Is there anything in the activity that creates a hierarchy between what is deemed 'female' and 'male' and that attaches greater value to the 'male'? Are there instances where men seem to be the norm and women treated as intruders? Here it is important to acknowledge hierarchies of power within the academic institution that privilege men and the masculine and devalue women and the feminine.
- How are resources that may have financial consequences (e.g. money, time, information and training) within the activity divided between women and men? Within different academic fields?
 - Are there any gender-related patterns in what and who is given priority with respect to time?

- Whose needs are being met and whose are not?
- Has the activity been designed on the basis of a norm that favours either men or women?
- Are women's and men's interests, opportunities and wishes met to an equal degree?
- Do women and men, as individuals and groups, encounter different demands and expectations linked to gender stereotypes that may have financial consequences?
- What are the prevailing norms and values that lead to some tasks being defined as 'female' and others as 'male'?

Step 3: What are the consequences?

- If there is evidence from step 2 that indicates gender inequality in relation to resources, it is now time in Step 3 to consider the reasons for the detected gender patterns and their impact. In this step we establish an understanding of which norms govern the activity.
 - Describe how the activity affects women and men, different academic fields, positions etc. Describe how the gender inequality manifests itself.
 - Women and men may frequently have the same rights and obligations but not the same opportunities. If this is the case, describe the consequences.
 - Which are the norms governing the activity? Utilise an analytical approach based on knowledge of power relationships between men and women.

Step 4: What can be done? Formulate new objectives and measures

- Share your findings with the appropriate parties and brainstorm how to proceed and what possibilities exist for change. List the changes that may enhance gender equality.
- Put forward a gender equality objective based on the gender patterns identified in the analysis.
- Examine your gender equality plan. Is it sufficient to work towards gender equality regarding this activity, or do you need to draw up new objectives?

Step 5: What measures to take?

Systematic change work is essential when an academic institution seeks to build up long-term gender budgeting in its core operation:

- Decide what measures from step 4 you intend to implement.
- Plan how and when they are to be implemented.

- Allocate time and resources. Plan training of relevant actors.
- Decide what measures are necessary to adjust distorted gender patterns.
- Establish a completion date for achievement of the objectives.

Step 6: How should results be measured?

- Decide how to follow up on the objectives and impact. How will the outcome be measured? Sex-disaggregated statistics are one way of measuring and monitoring results.
- What indicators are to be used to monitor the activity?
- Decide when and how evaluation and monitoring are to take place.

Step 7: Evaluate the outcome

- This step enables management to evaluate progress from a gender equality viewpoint. Senior staff is responsible for monitoring and evaluation, which may involve questions such as:
 - Follow-up – Have we achieved our objectives? What were the results of our work? How do we assess the quality of what we did?
 - Evaluation – What lessons can we learn? How do we make positive changes last? What can we learn from the process? What and how can we learn from the obstacles we encountered? What is the next step?
 - Disseminate results – How do we disseminate the outcome and the lessons learned throughout the organisation? How do we make the outcome sustainable? How do we celebrate our successes?

EXAMPLES OF GENDER BUDGETING IN ACADEMIC AND SCIENTIFIC INSTITUTIONS

In this section we offer examples of gender budgeting projects in academic and scientific institutions. The examples derive from data collected at all the participating GARCIA institutions, but the main focus is on the University of Iceland where the toolkit was developed. In the examples we follow the seven-step methodology introduced in the previous section. In the first two examples we provide detailed descriptions. In the other examples that follow we encourage the user to brainstorm on the implementation process, that is, what measures to take and how to evaluate the outcome.

Gender representation in decision making¹³

In this example we focus on gender representation. Although such an example alone cannot be considered a gender budgeting project, it is an important starting point in all gender equality work. In general, decision-makers within an academic environment may not feel inclined to take gender issues into account as academia is considered to be a meritocratic place. However, from a gender budgeting perspective, it is important that the people responsible for decision-making and finances are equally represented by gender. Parity between women and men is a necessary although not sufficient condition for gender equality.

Step 1: What to analyse

The gender representation within boards as well as the level of significance of these boards will be analysed. In this example it will be analysed from the perspective of seven academic institutions: Radboud University, The Netherlands, The Catholic University of Louvain, Belgium, ZRC SAZU, Slovenia, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia, The University of Trento, Italy, The University of Lausanne, Switzerland, and The University of Iceland.

Step 2: What is the current situation and what are the gender patterns?

While the organizational structures, managements and financial frameworks are highly divergent in the participating institutions, there is a strong gender imbalance observable in the highest management positions with women present but representing the minority. Most managerial and financial decision-making is in the hands of men, even in institutions that are led by women. In Lausanne, the percentage of women in governing decision-making organs does not exceed 26%, and is usually around 20%, but decreases further up the hierarchy. The percentage of female deans and presidents is below 10%.

¹³ Example is based on Benschop et al. (2016), Dubois-Shaik et al. (2016), Murgia et al. (2016), Hofman et al. (2016), Bataille et al. (2016) and Steinþórsdóttir et al. (2016b).

In the University of Trento, female board members are concentrated in governing bodies with little prestige such as those dealing with equal opportunities, ethical issues and the quality of teaching. Men dominate the more prestigious and influential boards such as those dealing with research funding, promotion, recruitment and evaluation.

University of Iceland gender composition of the decision making body in March 2015

Position	Male	Female	% men	% women
Rector		1	0%	100%
Vice rector	1		100%	0%
CEO	1		100%	0%
University Council -members	5	6	45%	55%
University Council –substitute members	6	2	75%	25%
Heads of the University Councils committees and commission members	5	1	83%	17%
University Councils committees and commissions - members	23	14	62%	38%
Deans of Schools	3	2	60%	40%
Head of faculties	17	8	68%	32%

As illustrated in the table above, a similar situation is apparent at the University of Iceland. Despite the fact that a woman occupied the highest position within the academic hierarchy in 2015, there was an underrepresentation of women in the other decision-making bodies. While women do form the majority of the University Council members, they form a minority when University substitute council members are taken into account.

In line with what we see in Iceland, in some other academic institutions, for instance the University of Trento, the gender imbalance is also visible in the lower governing bodies (see table below). At the STEM department, there are only six women (out of 54 members), but only four (two associate and two assistant professors) are in permanent positions and none of them has decision-making power. At SSH women are more numerous than in STEM (21 out of 55 members), but only few have decision-making power.

University of Trento: Governing Bodies of Departments by sex in March 2015

	STEM		SSH	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Director of department	1		1	
Vice-director of department	1		1	
Department board members	48	6	34	21
Delegate of director of department	18	2	15	8
Executive board (Giunta)	N.A.		6 ¹⁴	1
President of Degree Course committee	N.A. ¹⁵		6	0
Vice-president of degree course committee	N.A.		6	0
Head of research units	11	0	7	2
Coordinator/Director of doctoral school	1			1
Vice-coordinator of Doctoral school	1		1	
Members of doctoral school committee	11	1	18	2

Step 3: What are the consequences?

Gender may be overlooked or ignored in decision-making process which can have a negative effect on women's situation. Women and men have the same rights, but apparently not the same opportunities, to occupy the highest management positions. Women may be utilised as tokens creating an atmosphere that is surrounded by an aura of gender equality.¹⁶

Step 4: What can be done? Formulate new objectives and measures

- By outlining the composition of women and men on boards and in decision-making bodies inequality can be made visible in a very general way, and function as part of introducing a gender budgeting project.
- Examine selection procedures for the highest managerial positions, decision-making bodies and boards.
- Find ways to get an equal representation of men and women in decision-making bodies, boards and managerial positions. Continue to investigate by examining the mechanics and systematic gender inequality as described in the next examples.
- Acknowledge that an equal gender representation or equal access in itself will not be enough to provide the solution; rather the focus needs to be on more covert systematic inequality processes.

¹⁴ The Director of Department and the Administrative staff member are not included.

¹⁵ At the STEM there is not the Committees of degree courses, there are: one delegate to teaching activities (a man) and three responsible professor of the degree courses (all men).

¹⁶ Pétursdóttir (2009) developed the notion of aura of gender equality, to describe the phenomena in which men and women convince themselves that equality reigns despite practical evidence indicating otherwise.

Step 5: What measures to take?

A possible scenario...

Each decision making board, that not yet comprises of a 40%-60% gender representative compilation, should reach that target within a certain time frame. The heads of each board will monitor the progress.

Step 6: How is the result to be measured?

A possible scenario...

Assess the gender compilation of each board within a year.

Step 7: Evaluate the outcome

A possible scenario...

Relevant actors evaluate the progress and put forward a new objective within a certain timeframe. The evaluation and discussion could revolve around questions of why the progress has not been more successful, what measures can be taken, or if the situation has improved. Whether there is a reason to aim even further, for instance by aspiring an even more gender equal balance (50%-50%) within decision making boards. Discuss the need of expanding or limiting the number of seats for certain board positions. Would it for example be possible to hire two instead of one CEO, in order to reach a gender balance within that position?

State funding to academic institutions¹⁷

In some countries, e.g. Belgium and Iceland, academic institutions receive state funding for teaching based on a price tag that is multiplied by the number of students that opt for a particular academic field. It varies to what extent the state funding is transparent and to what extent the basis for the allocation is built on empirical grounds. In Iceland the price categories appear to be extensively detailed, while in Belgium they are less specific.

Step 1: What to analyse

State funding for teaching allocated to academic institutions. In this example it will be analysed from the perspective of two academic institutions: The University of Iceland and The Catholic University of Louvain in Belgium.

Step 2: What is the current situation and what are the gender patterns?

Belgium, The Catholic University of Louvain

The public allocation from the state to the Catholic University of Louvain is calculated by counting the proportion of financeable students. The 'value' of each student depends on the discipline s/he chooses. There are three categories largely originating from the various academic fields, and each representing different weight units (coefficients):

- A. For Bachelor and Master students in the SSH = one unit.
- B. For Bachelor students in STEM and complementary Masters outside of human sciences and doctoral formations = two units.
- C. For MA students in STEM and Health Sciences, as well as for students that are about to finish their Bachelor in a number of STEM and Health Science disciplines = three units.

Iceland, University of Iceland

The majority of the state funding to the University of Iceland is based on a funding formula for payments per full-time equivalent student. The formula is based on a classificatory system for the amount of funding the institution receives for a single full-time student depending on their discipline, as shown in the table on the following page. It is stated in the 2015 Icelandic State Budget proposal that the price categories are based on common benchmarks but that it also takes into account the structure of the disciplines within each category.¹⁸ The state, however, neither clarifies the basis for the allocation nor provides any empirical grounds for the price categories.

¹⁷ This example is based on Dubois-Shaik et al. (2016) and Steinþórsdóttir et al. (2016b).

¹⁸ The 2015 Icelandic State Budget Proposal.

The funding formula ('price categories') for full-time equivalent student 2015:

Price category	Price in ISK	Price proportion
Social- and human sciences, theology, law and other comparable disciplines	611.000	1.0
Computer Science, mathematics and other comparable disciplines	958.000	1.6
Education and other comparable disciplines	916.000	1.5
Nursing and other comparable disciplines	1.149.000	1.9
Natural sciences, engineering and other comparable disciplines	1.200.000	2.0
Medicine	1.649.000	2.7
Odontology	2.654.000	4.3

Information from 2013 reveals, as seen in the figures below, that horizontal gender segregation is still prevalent in both the Catholic University of Louvain and at the University of Iceland. STEM fields are male dominated, while the SSH fields are more **feminised**, i.e. in terms of gender structure and subject fields. However, slight varieties exist between academic institutions and the manner in which they categorize their academic positions, and therefore the categories may not be fully comparable.

Step 3: What are the consequences?

Although the two states apply different systems, the data reveals that the state funding is considerably higher for STEM students than SSH students. In Belgium the funding is two to three times higher for a STEM student than for a SSH student and in Iceland the annual funding for a student in STEM is 60-100% higher than the annual funding for SSH students. In this system STEM students, that is the male-dominated disciplines, are more valued than SSH students, the more feminised disciplines. The basis for the allocation is not clarified, nor are any empirical grounds for the categories provided, which is important in order to determine if the allocation in to the current model can be justified.

Subsequently, the distribution of funding to academic institutions, based on these criteria, can impact the student-teacher ratio. In interviews with key players at University of Iceland it became apparent that with less funding the disciplines have fewer opportunities to hire full time academic staff, which leads to an unfavourable student/teacher ratio especially within the disciplines that are situated in the lowest price category. For instance in 2013 the student/full-time teacher ratio at University of Iceland was 43:1 in SSH, while in STEM it was 21:1. A high student/teacher ratio can affect both the academic staff and the students. With more teaching responsibilities and teaching related academic housework, academics are likely to experience higher workloads and work pressure, as it leaves them with less time to work on research. This in turn may intensify the work pressure and lead to lower levels of job satisfaction and feelings of ill being, which may negatively influence the quality of teaching that students receive.

Step 4: What can be done? Formulate new objectives and measures

- It is important to acknowledge that academic fields in the current system are valued differently and that the system might be fostering inequality.
- There is a need to improve transparency and provide empirical grounds for the price categories. The cost of each discipline has to be evaluated in co-operation with all relevant actors. It is important that the gender perspective is taken into account and that the basis for the allocation is built on empirical grounds that are made available to the public.
- Find reasonable and realistic ways to correct the imbalanced student/teacher ratio in STEM and SSH within certain time frame.

Step 5: What measures to take?

A possible scenario...

Re-evaluate the costs of each student per field and build on empirical grounds. Invite relevant actors (The Icelandic Ministry of Finance and Economic Affairs and the Ministry of Education, Science and Culture and the Federation Wallonia Bruxelles in Belgium) to a meeting in order to make

them aware of the situation. Negotiate a time frame to investigate the origin of the price categories. Depending on the progress a new price category model can then be developed and implemented.

Step 6: How should results be measured?

A possible scenario...

Measure and monitor the new price category model and the student-teacher ratio.

Step 7: Evaluate the outcome

A possible scenario...

Evaluate the outcome of the project and decide on how to proceed. Should the consequences of the gender differences within subject fields be examined further or is the situation deemed acceptable?

System to allocate funding within academic institution¹⁹

Overall, there is a lack of transparency regarding the distribution of funding within the participating GARCIA institutions. This is problematic as transparency is a precondition for gender budgeting.

Step 1: What to analyse

The system to allocate funding within academic institutions will be analysed. In this example we will discuss the situation from the perspective of the Radboud University in The Netherlands.

Step 2: What is the current situation and what are the gender patterns?

The University board at Radboud University relies on an allocation model to distribute funds to faculties and support departments. For faculties, the division is based on three money streams: 1) teaching (42%), 2) research (33%), and 3) contract agreements (25%). Success rates in the second and third money streams do not impact the division of first money stream funds.

The allocation model to the faculties is partly transparent as far as it is based on performance indicators such as the number of enrolled students and graduates (teaching), and number of realized PhDs (research). Other parts of the allocation model are based on opaque decisions made in the past about basic facilities (for teaching) or strategic considerations (for research). About 33% of teaching funds and 70% of research funds are not transparent. The money allocated in this less transparent part has been relatively stable over the years, so faculties know what amount to expect. The third category of contract agreements is partly based on strategic choices of the university board and the rest has to do with specific developments in different disciplines. The argument for holding on to this rather opaque budget allocation is that it provides the necessary stability to guarantee that the budget covers personnel cost.

Step 3: What are the consequences?

When financial and decision making processes are not transparent it is impossible to evaluate how the academic institution utilizes public funding, and whether or not this is done in a manner that uses those resources efficiently. Furthermore, without information on how the distribution is established and without gender disaggregated data, it is impossible to investigate whether the distribution of funding impacts faculties, academics and students differently and if it impacts women and men, and/or gendered fields, differently.

Step 4: What can be done? Formulate new objectives and measures

- Collect and compile gender disaggregated data.
- Investigate and consider options in which stability and transparency go hand-in-hand successfully.

¹⁹ This example is based on Benschop et al (2016).

- Require relevant actors to provide transparency where possible.
- Consider how the allocation model impacts different fields and target groups (e.g. faculties, academic staff, students). The answer should be evidence-based.
- Consider the possibility that the allocation model might have gendered consequences. Does it promote equality, foster inequality or maintain the status quo? The answer should be evidence-based.
- Consider how the system was developed and based on what information. Consider if the reasons for that development are valid and still applicable today. Answers to these inquiries should be evidence-based.

Step 5: What measures to take?

Here relevant actors have to decide what objectives and measures from step 4 they want to prioritise and focus on, how they should be implemented, who is going to monitor and implement them, and within what time frame.

Step 6: How is the result to be measured?

Here relevant actors have to decide how to evaluate the outcomes of the measures from step 5, how to follow up on the results and within what time frame.

Step 7: Evaluate the outcome

Here relevant actors have to evaluate the progress of the measures and examine whether the objectives have been achieved. If not they need to go back to step 5 and repeat the process.

Distribution of research grants²⁰

Step 1: What to analyse

The distribution of research grants within the academic and scientific institutions will be analysed. In this example, the issue will be analysed from the perspective of four academic institutions: Radboud University, The Netherlands, The Catholic University of Louvain, Belgium, The University of Trento, Italy and The University of Iceland.

Step 2: What is the current situation and what are the gender patterns?

Academics in STEM receive considerably more research grants than academics in SSH (see table below). Furthermore, the majority of the granted projects are co-ordinated by male academic staff, which enhances their research opportunities and prestige. The difference between awarded grants to women and men is greater in STEM than SSH.

International, national and local research grants obtained in 2013 by academic institution, academic field and gender of the project manager²¹

Academic institution	International, national or local grants:	STEM		SSH	
		Project manager			
		Male	Female	Male	Female
Radboud University, The Netherlands	International	4	0	2	0
	National	19	3	1	2
	Local/internal	0	0	1	0
The Catholic University of Louvain, Belgium	International	17	0	4	1
	National	2	4	2	0
	Local/internal	48	7	6	3
The University of Trento, Italy	International	95	1	1	3
	National	22	0	6	0
	Local/internal	46	4	10	19
The University of Iceland	International	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
	National	31	6	5	4
	Local/internal	57	17	13	13

²⁰ Example is based on Benschop et al. (2016), Dubois-Shaik et al. (2016), Murgia et al. (2016) and Steinþórsdóttir et al. (2016b).

²¹ In the case of Trento University, the information is from the academic year 2013/2014.

As the figure below shows, the gender representation of the academic staff in 2013 reveals that both STEM and SSH are still male dominated fields in all the academic institutions.²² There are, however, more imbalances in STEM. It is worth noticing that there is a another gender dimension here, men occupy higher academic positions than women in both SSH and STEM. Therefore, equal gender representation of the academic staff in SSH at Catholic University of Louvain can therefore be misleading.

Step 3: What are the consequences?

The data reveals that the distribution of grants is a highly gendered phenomenon, and by rewarding men and male-dominated fields, the academic system creates indirect discrimination. Grants can have great impact on faculties and academics. Obtaining a grant can impact an academic's promotion, prestige, opportunities, the likelihood of research assistance, the supervision of PhD students and even result in more research time and less teaching as the latter can be allocated elsewhere. Furthermore, mostly assigning grants to male-dominated fields could result in knowledge from female researchers and researchers in more feminised fields being created to a lesser degree.

Example of further implications: The funding can have further implications. The findings revealed that University of Iceland has the most performance-based incentives related to grants out of all the GARCIA participating institutions. Grants awarded to academics impact the distribution of funding within the academic institution. The academic schools receive 'matching funds' for grants, that is 60% of the grant value for international competitive grants, 35% for national competitive grants and 20% for other grants. This means that each faculty that secures grants will receive additional funding as a matching fund from the academic institution, which is taken from the government appropriation. This, therefore, results in a higher allocation of funding to the STEM faculties. Other faculties that obtain few grants or none at all, especially from international competitive funds, do not receive this financial compensation. Hence, not only is the

²² The data includes full-professors, associate professors and assistant professors at all the academic institutions. In addition, post-docs and assistant with PhD's are included in the data from The Catholic University of Louvain.

extramural funding much higher for the STEM than the SSH, but the funding also directs the distribution of public resources. There are more male academic staff members in STEM, though it has fewer students, most of whom are men. This means they enjoy a more favourable full-time teacher/student ratio than SSH. The school's access to funding also means more opportunities and time for research and hence for publication. Moreover, the UI system of matching funding rewards those who are already successful in obtaining funding; funding begets funding. At the University of Trento in Italy, a similar outcome is observable as the success rate in attaining third party funding partially affects the allocation of public research funds. This results in lower allocation to research teams in SSH than in STEM.

Step 4: What can be done? Formulate new objectives and measures

- Examine the research funds and awarded research grants in more detail. Further analyse the success rate of women and men and STEM and SSH, amount granted in relation to amount applied for and the number of applicants in relation to the applicant pool by gender and gendered academic fields. Consider if the distribution of funding is acceptable or if there is a gender bias. Make sure the answer is evidence based.
- Examine further what grants are open to different schools and scholars, and consider what could explain any discrepancy and if there is a possible gender bias. Make sure the answer is evidence based.
- Consider how the grants influence different fields and target groups (e.g. faculties, academic staff, students) and if there is a possible gender bias. Consider the possibility that the distribution of grants might have gendered consequences. Does it promote equality, foster inequality or maintain the status quo?
- Consider the governmental policies behind allocation of research funding: Are there different priorities when resources are distributed to different academic fields, such as the natural sciences and the social and human sciences? What is the justification for that? Consider what that justification is based on.
- Consider the premises upon which the research fund's policies are based, and how the strategies and criteria developed. Determine if there is a possible gender bias. Make sure the answer is evidence based.
- Evaluate the decision-making process and who makes the decisions. Consider if the expert panels need gender sensitivity training.
- Consider if the institutional support system, such as advisors and funding, is the same for all academic fields.

Step 5: What measures to take?

Here relevant actors have to decide what objectives and measures from step 4 should be implemented, how they should be implemented and within what time frame.

Step 6: How should results be measured?

Here relevant actors have to decide how to evaluate the outcomes of the measures from step 5, how to follow up on the results and within what time frame.

Step 7: Evaluate the outcome

Here relevant actors have to evaluate the progress of the measures and if the objectives have been achieved.

Evaluation of the work of academics²³

The evaluation of the work of academics can have great impact on the academic staff's careers and financial situation, as well as on the distribution of funding within the academic institutions. At the University of Iceland, this evaluation influences academics directly and distribution of public funding to the academic schools. At The University of Trento academics performance influences allocations of research funds within the faculties. At other institutions the pressure with regard to 'excellence' is more informal such as at Radboud University, The Catholic University of Louvain, The University of Lausanne, The Research centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts and The University of Ljubljana, Slovenia.

Step 1: What to analyse

Evaluation of the work of academics from the perspective of University of Iceland and Trento University, while also being alert to what part of the work is left out of the official evaluations.

Step 2: What is the current situation and what are the gender patterns?

The University of Iceland

At the University of Iceland the work of academics is evaluated in terms of research, teaching, administration and service. The evaluation is based on an incentive point system, in which research activities are considered the most valuable activities, and therefore awarded the most points. The system has great impact on the academic's career and work-life balance and the allocation of public funding within the University. Being a successful researcher has positive effects on promotion, salaries, payment from productivity evaluation funds, sabbaticals, work obligations, chances of obtaining funding, as well as the amount of funding to which their faculty is entitled.

Academics are assigned a fixed amount of research points for their teaching duties (10 points a year for a fulltime position and 5 points for a part-time position) and supervision of postgraduate students. Extra teaching duties do not display themselves in additional research points but are paid out in overtime. The publication of teaching materials and innovation in teaching may also be rewarded. The evaluation of research-related activities are built on performance measurements, such as the amount of attained international competitive funding, citations, and ranking and impact factor of journals/publishing houses where academics publish their work. The higher the publication outlet's impact factor, the more research points are awarded. Special research points, referred to as 'major points', are awarded for articles in 'prestigious' publications.

The table below presents the number of research points and major points awarded to the academics in the STEM and the SSH. The mean number of research points per academic in the STEM is 27% higher than that in the SSH, and the mean number of major points per academic staff member in the STEM is 60% higher than that in the SSH. STEM academics have 70% of its research points in the category of 'major points' compared to 55% for the SSH academics.

23 Example is based on Murgia et al. (2016) and Steinþórsdóttir et al. (2016b).

Mean research points and major points in SSH and STEM in 2013

Academic school	Number of staff members who submit the evaluation report	Equivalent of a full-time position	Research points in 2013			Major points in 2013			
			Research points	Average number of research points/ number of academic staff	Average number of research points/ equivalent of a full-time position	Major points	Average number of major points/ number of academic staff	Average number of major points/ equivalent of a full-time position	% major points of research points
SSH	112	108	3.777	29	35	2.076	16	19	55%
STEM	112	110	4.563	37	41	3.173	25	29	70%

As can be seen in the figure below, STEM is male dominated and SSH is more feminised. The higher positions have more research time, while the more precarious positions, such as the positions of adjuncts and sessional teachers, are more focused on teaching and are not part of the research evaluation system. Men, in both STEM and SSH, more often occupy these higher positions while women are in the more precarious positions. Furthermore, the student/teacher ratio is considerably more favourable for STEM than SSH, with it being 21:1 in STEM and 43:1 in SSH, which means that academic staff in SSH are likely to spend more time on teaching related academic housework than academic staff in STEM, which in turn leaves them with less time to put into research. While academics in high positions are likely to be able to outsource some of their academic housework, academics in the lower ranks are less likely to have the possibility to do so.

The University of Trento, Italy

At The University of Trento STEM and SSH departments, the work of academics is evaluated to allocate research funds within the faculties. The criteria for the allocation and the performance indicators are shown in the table below.

Allocation systems and performance indicators in STEM and SSH

Allocation		
	STEM	SSH
Individual level	Fixed amount, ca. 2.000 EUR annually. Regardless of productivity.	Fixed amount, ca. 500 EUR annually. Regardless of productivity.
Research unit level	Funds allocated to research units based on their productivity over the past year measured through performance composite index. It is computed on individual basis: Academics can be part of 1-3 research units, with a weight in each research unit proportional to his/her share. The membership percentage identifies the scale through which each person contributes to the reach unit performance index.	Additional funding is distributed on the basis of index of individual performance. Refers to the last five years.
Performance composite index/ Index of individual performance.		
	STEM	SSH
Performance indicators, criteria:	Based on the individual academics performance.	Based on the individual academics performance
Publications	Books, book chapters, patents, papers in A, B, C ranked journals and conference publications (in order of importance). Publications and projects are the most important criteria.	Books (A and B rank editor); papers in journals (ranked in A and B); book editorship and book chapters (A and B rank editor); research reports and working papers (in order of importance) 70% of the weighted criteria.
Projects	Project financing institution (local, national, European; public or private) and its total amount. Publications and projects are the most important criteria.	Based on the scale of funding received in the last five years. 30% of the weighted criteria.
Project calls		Symbolic reward (appr. 1.000-1.500 euro) for projects presented in competitive calls that receive a positive evaluation, but are not funded.
Teaching	Number of courses, the number of credits assigned for each course, the number of students attending the course.	<i>Not measured.</i>
'Adjustment factors': Institutional assignments and awards	The professors, which hold an institutional position (e.g. Director of Department, Delegate of the Rector, etc.), receive additional scores and the professors who acquire particular awards, participate at international conferences etc. receive additional scores.	<i>Not measured.</i>

As can be seen in the figure below, STEM is male dominated and SSH is more feminised, as is the case in Iceland. The academic staff (full professors, associate professors, assistant professors, post-doc and temporary lecturers) in SSH are 63% men and 37% women, and in STEM are 85% men and 15% women. Men occupy the higher positions and women are in the more precarious positions. However, the student/teacher ratio is nearly identical for STEM and SSH, with the ratio of 21:1 in STEM versus 22:1 in SSH.

Step 3: What are the consequences?

From the data collected at The University of Iceland and the University of Trento, we can see how working conditions of academics can have extensive consequences. Both at the institutional level, where the evaluation impacts distribution of funding, and at the individual academic level, where the evaluation can influence the academics day to day work-life, opportunities and future.

At University of Iceland, the different number of research points and major points awarded to academics and the proportion of major points acquired by academics in SSH and STEM could indicate that either the academics in the STEM are more active researchers than their colleagues in the SSH, or that the evaluation of research activities is more favourable to STEM as there is the tendency of multi-authorship and the highest evaluated journals are STEM orientated. As for both horizontal and vertical segregation, this system of rewarding research to the highest extent, in combination with a high student/teacher ratio in SSH, means that this system is negatively affecting women in academia. There are indeed strong indications of the system's internal gender bias as men are more numerous in the STEM which has fewer students, most of whom are men, which likely results in STEM academics having more time for research than the SSH academics

At the University of Trento, the evaluation of work of academics differs considerably in the male-dominated STEM and more feminised SSH. In STEM, the performance index is based not only on publications and projects, but it also includes teaching and institutional activities. While in SSH, the performance index is only based on publication and project criteria, and the weight of each category is clearly defined. Teaching is not part of the evaluation of more feminised SSH, while it is in the male

dominated STEM. The STEM system takes more academic work-related activities into account than the SSH system. This indicates that more tasks performed within the male dominated fields are valued, while the same tasks performed within the more feminised fields are not.

Step 4: What can be done? Formulate new objectives and measures

- Analyse further the results of the evaluation systems by gender, gendered academic fields, academic positions, employment period etc. It would show a more nuanced picture of this system. Consider what could explain the discrepancy, if there is any, and if there is a possible gender bias. Make sure the answer is evidence based.
- Examine further the performance measurements. Consider what work is valued and what is not valued and how work and workloads are valued or undervalued. Consider how it impacts different academic fields and academics in different positions. Take the time aspect into account and consider on what information and data the criteria are developed. Consider if the criteria is acceptable or if there is a possible gender bias. Make sure the answer is evidence based.
- Evaluate the decision making process and who makes the decisions. Consider if there is need for gender sensitive training.

Step 5: What measures to take?

Here relevant actors have to decide what objectives and measures from step 4 they want to prioritise and focus on, how they should be implemented, who is going to monitor and implement them, and within what time frame.

Step 6: How should results be measured?

Here relevant actors have to decide how to evaluate the outcomes of the measures from step 5, how to follow up on the results and within what time frame.

Step 7: Evaluate the outcome

Here relevant actors have to evaluate the progress of the measures and examine whether the objectives have been achieved. If not they need to go back to step 5 and repeat the process.

Financial resources for PhD students and duration of PhD programme²⁴

The status of PhD students differs between countries and academic institutions. At some academic institutions, such as Radboud University, the PhD candidates are considered employees, receive salary and have a temporary employment contract. At the University of Trento, the PhD candidates receive a scholarship. At The Catholic University of Louvain, The University of Iceland and The University of Lausanne the status of PhD candidates can vary from being a paid employee, to receiving grants for the whole or part of the PhD program, to relying on student-loans or/and other paid labour either within or outside the academic institution. PhD candidates in the male dominated fields of STEM tend to be better off financially. For instance, at the University of Iceland most PhD candidates in STEM receive salary or have a grant, while this is not the case in SSH. At the University of Lausanne there is a similar pattern observable with more PhD candidates lacking a contract in SSH than in STEM. Funding is very important for PhD candidates to succeed and it can deeply affect the duration of their programme, and whether or not they complete the course of study successfully.

Step 1: What to analyse

Financial resources for PhD students and the duration of PhD programme will be analysed. In this example the perspective of The University of Iceland and The University of Lausanne, Switzerland are discussed.

Step 2: What is the current situation and what are the gender patterns?

The University of Iceland

At the University of Iceland, PhD positions can either be funded, paid through employment or non-paid. In STEM almost all the PhD students have funding, and funding is currently a precondition for the enrolment of PhD students in STEM, while this is not the case in SSH. Funded PhD positions rely most often on Icelandic funding, such as that of the University of Iceland's research fund from which PhD grants are awarded annually. The evaluation of the application is based on the three main criteria: Expert review of the application, the supervisor's publication output and the students' grades and publication output. As shown in the table on the next page, in 2013 more applications are received from STEM than in SSH, and more PhD grants go to STEM than SSH. Furthermore, the majority of the supervisors granted and most successful applicants were men and in full professor positions.

²⁴ Example is based on Steinþórsdóttir et al. (2016b) and Bataille et al. (2016).

University of Iceland: Number of doctoral grants applicants, funded projects and success rate by supervisors academic position and sex 2013.

	Applicants			Funded projects			Success rate	
	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women
SSH	14	10	24	3	2	5	21%	20%
Assistant professor	3	1	4				0%	0%
Associate professor	6	1	7	1		1	17%	0%
Full professor	5	8	13	2	2	4	40%	25%
STEM	30	9	39	10	1	11	33%	11%
Assistant professor	1		1				0%	
Associate professor	4	5	9	1		1	25%	0%
Full professor	18	4	22	8	1	9	44%	25%
Research specialist	1		1				0%	
Research Scholar	3		3				0%	
Research Scientist	3		3	1		1	33%	

This is a trend that is observable in other funds as well. Many factors can affect the length of a PhD program, but according to the interviewees of the GARCIA project, funding is a major factor. As shown in the table below, for the years 2010–2013 the PhD duration of SSH candidates are on average considerably longer than for STEM candidates and on average longer for women than men. It is important to note that STEM is a male dominated field, and SSH a more feminised field, which is also reflected in the number of PhD students. In STEM men are the majority of PhD students (58% in 2013) and PhD graduates (61%), compared to SSH where women are the majority of PhD students (72%) and PhD graduates (75%) (not displayed in the tables).

University of Iceland: Percentage of PhD students and duration of their PhD programme 2010-2013 according to school and gender

		<5 years	>5 years
SSH	Women	16.7%	83.3%
	Men	22.2%	77.8%
STEM	Women	46.4%	53.6%
	Men	62.5%	37.5%

University of Lausanne, Switzerland

Around half of the doctoral candidates do not have an employment contract at the University. That, however, varies across faculties, with 69% of candidates in the Arts & Humanities and 35% in Geosciences and Environment not having a contract. The average duration of a PhD programme is 8.8 semesters (four and a half years) for STEM candidates, but 9.7 semesters (almost 5 years) for SSH candidates.

University of Lausanne: Number of PhD students, full-time and part-time, and number of PhD graduations by sex in SSH and STEM in 2013.

	SSH		STEM	
	Men	Women	Men	Women
Full-time PhD	4	7	51	40
Part-time PhD	1	2	51	64
PhD graduation	9	18	68	65

Step 3: What are the consequences?

The data reveals that PhD students in male dominated fields are more likely to have funding than PhD students in more feminised fields. If PhD students in male dominated fields are more often funded than PhD students in the more feminised fields, the academic system is creating indirect discrimination. Funding can strongly impact the duration of a PhD programme, and the data reveals that the duration of the programme for PhD students in SSH is longer than for STEM students. Furthermore, the University of Iceland's data reveal that the duration of the PhD programme is on average longer for women than men in both SSH and STEM. By having a secure and sufficient income during the PhD, students are more likely to spend their time on research and writing rather than on finding a different income source, by e.g. teaching, applying for grants, which are time-consuming activities. Furthermore, by mostly assigning grants to men and male-dominated fields, there is a risk that knowledge from female researchers and researchers in more feminised fields is being created to a lesser degree.

Step 4: What can be done? Formulate new objectives and measures

- Examine further the sources of income for PhD students. Analyse which PhD positions are paid, funded and non-paid according to academic fields and gender. If a position is non-paid, analyse further the sources of income. Consider if the status of the PhD students within the academic institution is acceptable and if there is a gender bias. Make sure the answer is evidence based.
- Consider how sources of income influence PhD students from different fields and if there is a possible gender bias.
- Consider if the institutional support system of PhD students, on applying for funding, is the same for all academic fields.
- Examine further research funds and awarded research grants to PhD students. Analyse further the success rate by gender and academic field, amount granted in relation to amount applied for and the number of applicants in relation to the applicant pool by gender and gendered academic fields. Consider if the distribution of funding is acceptable or if there is a gender bias. Make sure that the outcome is evidence based.
- Examine further what grants are open to PhD students from different schools, and consider what could explain this discrepancy and if there is a possible gender bias. Make sure the answer is evidence based.

- Consider on what premises the academic institutions policies related to the funding of the PhD programme are developed and if there is a possible gender bias.
- Evaluate the decision making process and who makes the decisions. Consider if there is a need for gender sensitive training.

Step 5: What measures to take?

Here relevant actors have to decide what objectives and measures from step 4 they want to prioritise and focus on, how they should be implemented, who is going to monitor and implement them, and within what time frame.

Step 6: How should results be measured?

Here relevant actors have to decide how to evaluate the outcomes of the measures from step 5, how to follow up on the results and within what time frame.

Step 7: Evaluate the outcome

Here relevant actors have to evaluate the progress of the measures and examine whether the objectives have been achieved. If not they need to go back to step 5 and repeat the process.

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